

Street-level weather station network in Bristol, UK: Station documentation

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Detailed attribution see Page 2.

Abstract

The topography of Bristol, UK, located in a basin and separated from the Bristol Channel by hills and a narrow gorge, creates a unique climate where urban effects occur along with orographic, and coastal effects. To support research on high-resolution atmospheric modelling of urban weather, climate and hydrology, since 2024 an automatic weather station network is operated in the Greater Bristol area, jointly managed by the Universities of Freiburg, Reading and Bristol with support from Bristol City Council. This report documents all 47 stations with their position, address, land cover, orography as well as nearby objects that are relevant for data interpretation. Of the 47 stations, 39 were installed in 2024, six in 2025 and two in 2026. Maps are provided for each weather station detailing the location within the network, the local-scale siting, and the microscale urban surrounding. The report documents mounting structures, sensors operated, operation periods and changes. Station photographs and sky-view images provide details on the siting and surroundings.

Keywords: Urban weather station network, automatic weather station, street-level weather station, meta-data, site documentation, Bristol, UK

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Bristol - Landsdowne Court	25-BRLACO
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Bristol - Montpelier.....	28-BRMONT
Bristol - Old Market.....	29-BROLDM
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Bristol - Severnside	36-BRSEVS
Bristol - Stoke Gifford.....	37-BRSGIF
Bristol - St Georges Park	38-BRSGPA
Bristol - Shirehampton.....	39-BRSHIR
Bristol - Southville	40-BRSOVI
Bristol - Stanton Drew.....	41-BRSTAN
Bristol - Stoke Bishop	42-BRSTBI
Bristol - Stockwood	43-BRSTOC
Bristol - Tyndall Park	44-BRTYND
Bristol - Tyntesfield	45-BRTYNT
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Network overview map

Figure 1: Map of the locations of all 47 street-level weather stations in the Greater Bristol area as of June 1, 2026. Map (a) shows the entire domain including sites in Bristol City, South Gloucestershire, North Somerset and Bath & North East Somerset Council areas. Map (b) enlarges the location of sites in a subset covering city centre and along Avon Gorge. Built-up areas are shown in red. Background: Copernicus Land Monitoring Service - Urban Atlas Land Cover/Land Use.

Abbreviations, definitions and measurement units

- **Coordinates** are given in decimal degrees (according to the Coordinate Reference System (CRS) WGS84).
- **All times given in datasets and this report refer to UTC**
- **Sensors deployed:** Pessl nMeteos 180 by Pessl Instruments, Weiz, Austria.
- **Topographic elevation** refers to the ground level in meters above mean sea level and was extracted from a digital elevation model.
- **Elevation above ground** refers to the vertical offset of the mounting structure base ground level from the surrounding ground level.
- **Local Climate Zones (LCZ)** refer to Stewart and Oke, 2012² and have been subjectively mapped by the authors.
- **Urban Atlas Classes** refer to Montero et al, 2014³ and the 2018 version⁵ or 2021 version⁶. For BRSTAN the 2006 version⁷ of the Urban Atlas is used due to geographic unavailability of later versions.
- **Center of mounting structure base** refers to the horizontal center of the respective pole at ground level.
- **x:** Horizontal distance in meters from center of mounting structure base.
- **z:** Vertical distance in meters from center of mounting structure base.
- **α :** Azimuth of respective object relative to mounting structure given in degrees (accuracy: approx. 20°).

External sources and tools

- Source of background for *aerial photographs*: Google Earth¹ 2024 and 2026.
- Source of background for *local-scale maps*: OSM⁹.
- Sky View factors were calculated from hemispherical photos at the location of the top of the Pessl nMeteos 180 rain gauge, using the calculation method according to RayManPro¹⁰⁻¹².
- All maps were created using QGIS⁸.

1: Google Earth, ©2024 Google Imagery, Airbus, Maxar Technology ©2024

2: Stewart, I.D., Oke, T.R., 2012. Local climate zones for urban temperature studies. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 93, 1879–1900.

3: Montero, E., Van Wavelaer, J., Garzón, A., 2014. *The European Urban Atlas*. Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht. pp. 115–124.

4: Copernicus Urban Atlas Land Cover / Land Use 2021 (vector), Europe, 3-yearly 2021 Vector 10.2909/05ae1ee1-e550-4e66-b74d-4926322d981a

5: Copernicus Urban Atlas Land Cover / Land Use 2021 (vector), Europe, 3-yearly [10.2909/05ae1ee1-e550-4e66-b74d-4926322d981a](https://doi.org/10.2909/05ae1ee1-e550-4e66-b74d-4926322d981a)

6: Copernicus Urban Atlas Land Cover / Land Use 2018 (vector), Europe, 3-yearly [10.2909/fb4dffa1-6ceb-4cc0-8372-1ed354c285e6](https://doi.org/10.2909/fb4dffa1-6ceb-4cc0-8372-1ed354c285e6)

7: Copernicus Urban Atlas Land Cover / Land Use 2006 (vector), Europe, 6-yearly [10.2909/551d6741-84d0-43fb-bda8-1768d51bbb4c](https://doi.org/10.2909/551d6741-84d0-43fb-bda8-1768d51bbb4c)

8: QGIS.org (2026). QGIS Geographic Information System. Open Source Geospatial Foundation Project. <http://qgis.org>

9: OpenStreetMap. For detailed copyright see <https://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>

10: Matzarakis, A., Rutz, F., Mayer, H., 2007: Modelling Radiation fluxes in simple and complex environments - Application of the RayMan model. *International Journal of Biometeorology* 51, 323-334.

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12: Matzarakis, A., Gangwisch, M., Fröhlich, D., 2021: RayMan and SkyHelios Model. In: Palme, M., Salvati, A. (eds) *Urban Microclimate Modelling for Comfort and Energy Studies*. Springer, Cham., 339-361,

Bristol – Ashton Vale (BRASHV)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRASHV	Full name	Bristol – Ashton Vale
Latitude	51.439283°N	Longitude	2.62703°W
Topographic elevation	8.9 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	41 Ashton Vale Rd, Bristol BS3 2HT, UK	Administrative unit	Bedminster
Local Climate Zone	8 (Large low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	12100
Sky view factor	0.696	Dominant land use	Industrial / Warehouses
Orographic setting	Flat in valley bottom	Artificial heat sources	Cars, Industrial venting
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	8 m	Parking space:	2 m
		Tree:	25 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Warehouse / light industrial district on western Edge of Bristol. Station located on curved street with large low-rise industrial buildings / warehouses and parking spaces on either sides.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Black lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	8.1 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.1 m	Light extension offset 0.5 m, $\alpha = 165^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.42 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 95^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.38 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 130^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-20 12:30 UTC	2025-02-28 14:40 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C6D	2024-05-20 12:30 UTC Station installation
2025-02-28 15:05 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C55	2024-11-21 Service: Sensor appears to have been vandalized (data transmission stopped on 2024-08-03, 00:30). Wires have been snipped from battery case to device
			2025-02-28 14:40 UTC Service: Sensor swap, new battery
			2025-07-01 13:40 to 2025-07-01 14:30 UTC Service: Cleaning, blocked rain gauge
			2026-02-10 11:40 to 2026-02-10 11:50 UTC Service: Battery replacement, blocked rain gauge, cleaning
			2026-05-12 11:20 to 2026-05-12 11:55 UTC Service: Battery replacement (station stopped transmitting data on 2026-05-04 12:45 UTC), cleaning, blocked rain gauge, system restart, no external signs of damage reported

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-20)

From East
(2024-05-20)

From South
(2024-05-20)

From West
(2024-05-20)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-20)

Bristol – Avon Gorge (BRAVGO)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRAVGO	Full name	Bristol – Avon Gorge
Latitude	51.46708°N	Longitude	2.632238°W
Topographic elevation	14.1m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address		Administrative unit	Stoke Bishop
Local Climate Zone	C (Bush, scrub)	Urban Atlas Class	23000
Sky view factor	0.621	Dominant land use	Recreational
Orographic setting	At bottom of narrow gorge / valley	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	Parking space:	100 m	Tree: 30 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Large curved gorge (Avon) with two-way major road and parking spots, rock cliffs approx. 20 m east of location. Some forested patches, large forest to the W.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	12 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.16 m	Light extension offset 1.5 m, $\alpha = 255^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.43 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 125^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 160^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-17 15:30 UTC	2026-05-31 23:59 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C91	2024-05-17 15:30 UTC Station installation 2025-06-17 13:40 to 2025-06-17 13:50 UTC Service: Battery replacement 2026-03-18 13:13 to 2026-03-18 13:35 UTC Service: Battery replacement, cleaning, filter was pretty clean, but the tipping bucket wasn't operating well due to spider webs.

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-17)

From East
(2024-05-17)

From South
(2024-05-17)

From West
(2024-05-17)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-17)

Bristol – Avonmouth (BRAVOM)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRAVOM	Full name	Bristol – Avonmouth
Latitude	51.512702°N	Longitude	2.695766°W
Topographic elevation	8.1 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	St Andrew's Rd, Avonmouth, BS11 9HS, UK	Administrative unit	Avonmouth and Lawrence Weston
Local Climate Zone	8 (Large low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	12100
Sky view factor	0.797	Dominant land use	Industrial / Warehouses
Orographic setting	Flat, near shoreline	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building: 25 m		Parking space: 4 m	Tree: 10 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Major port, industry and transit area with railway lines and harbour basins. Station located on curved street along railway with large low-rise industrial buildings to the E, a bulk cement factory and railway line to the W and warehouses and parking spaces.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Dark grey lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	10 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.11 m	Light extension offset 1.5 m, $\alpha = 115^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.47 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 40^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.37 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 75^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-16 13:40 UTC	2025-01-31 11:15 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C45	2024-05-16 13:40 UTC Station installation
2025-01-31 11:45 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C74	2024-12-17 Battery depleted
			2025-01-31 11:15 to 2025-01-31 11:45 UTC Service: Sensor swap, new battery
			2026-03-18 13:57 to 2026-03-18 14:04 UTC Service: Battery replacement, cleaning, upon arrival the radiation shield on the T/RH Sensor was bent over so that it was on its side. Bent back to normal orientation.

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-16)

From East
(2024-05-16)

From South
(2024-05-16)

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-16)

Bristol – Barton Hill (BRBART)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRBART	Full name	Bristol – Barton Hill
Latitude	51.455489°N	Longitude	2.562216°W
Topographic elevation	24.8 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Beam St, Redfield, Bristol BS5 9QY, UK	Administrative unit	Lawrence Hill
Local Climate Zone	4 (Open high-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	12100
Sky view factor	0.610	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat at valley bottom	Artificial heat sources	-
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	25 m	Parking space:	5 m
		Tree:	7 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Redeveloped residential area with four isolated high-rise buildings surrounding station located in small greenspace with grass surface, nearby parking lots, some tall trees.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Dark grey lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	5.5 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.08 m	Light extension offset 0.7 m, $\alpha = 215^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 100^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 135^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-23 12:00 UTC	2025-04-02 15:40 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C61	2025-04-02 15:45 to 2025-04-02 15:50 UTC Service: Sensor swap, new battery
2025-04-02 15:55 UTC	2025-07-01 13:00 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C60	2025-07-01 13:30 to 2025-07-01 13:40 UTC Service: Sensor swap, new battery
2025-07-01 13:10 UTC	2025-12-03 11:00 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13D4A	2025-10-10 Station identified as damaged, pictures taken, base plate fell off and needs repair (no swap, last data 2025-09-18 05:15 UTC)
2025-12-03 11:45 UTC		Pessl nMetos180 04D13C5C	2025-12-03 11:25 to 2025-12-03 11:40 UTC Service: Sensor swap, new battery

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-23)

From East
(2024-05-23)

From South
(2024-05-23)

From West
(2024-05-23)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-23)

Bristol – Bedminster East (BRBEDE)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRBEDE	Full name	Bristol – Bedminster East
Latitude	51.443828°N	Longitude	2.589581°W
Topographic elevation	8.9 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	10 Whitehouse St, Bristol, UK	Administrative unit	Southville
Local Climate Zone	5 (Open midrise)	Urban Atlas Class	12100
Sky view factor	0.797	Dominant land use	Industrial/ Commercial
Orographic setting	Flat at valley bottom	Artificial heat sources	-
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	7 m	Parking space:	1 m
		Tree:	4 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Wide N-S-oriented street in an inner-city industrial / warehouse area. Sports facilities nearby. Area undergoing urban redevelopment with new zoning.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Dark grey lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	12 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.12 m	Light extension offset 1.5 m, $\alpha = 285^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.41 m, z = 3.45 m, $\alpha = 5^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.37 m, z = 3.33 m, $\alpha = 40^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-23 13:40 UTC	2025-03-27 14:40 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C60	2024-05-23 13:40 UTC Station installation
2025-03-27 15:00 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C99	2024-09-03 21:15 UTC Station stopped transmitting data
			2024-11-21 Service: battery replacement
			2025-03-27 14:40 to 2025-03-27 15:00 UTC Service: Sensor swap, battery replacement
			2026-03-18 10:05 to 2026-03-18 10:20 UTC Service: Cleaning, battery replacement

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-23)

From East
Not available

From South
(2024-05-23)

From West
(202-04-03)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-23)

Bristol – Bedminster West (BRBEDW)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRBEDW	Full name	Bristol – Bedminster West
Latitude	51.438577°N	Longitude	2.607304°W
Topographic elevation	28.5 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	18 Ruby St Bristol BS3 3DY UK	Administrative unit	Bedminster
Local Climate Zone	3 (Compact low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	12220
Sky view factor	0.629	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	5 m	Parking space:	1 m
		Tree:	>50 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Inner-city dense and uniform residential area characterized by terraced houses. Only small gardens. Station on E-W-oriented residential street with 2-story attached buildings and street parking on both sides.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Silver lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset 0.4 m, $\alpha = 135^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 30^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 65^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-20 18:20 UTC	2025-02-18 14:00 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C57	2024-05-20 18:20 UTC Station installed
2025-02-18 15:00 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C58	2025-02-18 14:30 to 2025-02-18 14:58 UTC Sensor swap: Replaced battery
			2026-04-10 Station reported as damaged (since 2026-04-02 10:00 UTC)
			2026-04-13 13:15 UTC Removal of 04D13C58 from site for repair
			2026-04-23 11:45 to 2026-04-23 12:01 UTC Re-Installation of 04D13C58: System restart

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
Not available

From East
(2024-05-20)

From South
(2024-05-20)

From West
(2024-05-20)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-20)

Bristol – Brentry (BRBREN)**Station location and siting**

Station ID	BRBREN	Full name	Bristol – Brentry
Latitude	51.511192°N	Longitude	2.614673°W
Topographic elevation	44.9 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	25 Marlwood Dr, Bristol BS10 6SH, UK	Administrative unit	Henbury & Brentry
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	12220
Sky view factor	0.771	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Slight slope to NE	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	6 m	Parking space:	2 m
		Tree:	7 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Relatively uniform suburban residential area. N-S oriented road, 2-story residential duplex and triplex buildings with front gardens or driveways. Large gardens.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Light grey lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset 0.8 m, $\alpha = 120^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 35^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 70^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-17 12:00 UTC	2025-01-30 12:05 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13D4A	2024-05-17 12:00 UTC Station installation
2025-01-30 12:25 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C93	2024-10-04 10:10 UTC Service: Battery replacement
			2025-01-30 12:05 to 2025-01-30 12:25 UTC Sensor swap, battery replacement, sensor was damaged
			2026-03-18 14:33 to 2026-03-18 14:39 UTC Service: Battery replacement, Cleaning, filter was pretty clean

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-17)

From East
(2024-05-17)

From South
(2024-05-17)

From West
(2024-05-17)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-17)

Bristol – Brislington (BRBRIS)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRBRIS	Full name	Bristol – Brislington
Latitude	51.444226°N	Longitude	2.55382°W
Topographic elevation	24.8 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	1 Cuffington Ave, Brislington, Bristol BS4 3QY, UK	Administrative unit	Brislington West
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.767	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Slight slope to NW	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	4 m	Parking space:	2 m
		Tree:	10 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Hillside residential inner-city area with dominantly terraced houses, North-south-oriented street with 2-story row and duplex buildings and medium to large vegetated backyards.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Black lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset 0.8 m, $\alpha = 225^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 155^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 180^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-23 10:10 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C59	2024-05-23 10:10 UTC Station installation
			2024-08-15 14:20 to 2024-08-15 14:30 UTC Service: Battery replacement
			2025-12-16 11:45 to 2025-12-16 12:00 UTC Service: Battery replacement, cleaning, blocked rain gauge

Maps

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
Not available

From East
Not available

From South
(2024-05-23)

From West
(2024-05-23)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-23)

Bristol – Cadbury Heath (BRCADB)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRCADB	Full name	Bristol – Cadbury Heath
Latitude	51.442972°N	Longitude	2.485198°W
Topographic elevation	48 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	31 Far Handstones, Barrs Court, Bristol BS30 8AR, UK	Administrative unit	South Gloucestershire, Longwell Green
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11220
Sky view factor	0.930	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	3 m	Parking space:	3 m
		Tree:	- m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Medium-density suburban residential area characterized by semi-detached and detached houses. Moderate gardens and green space. Station on a curving residential street with 2-story houses, driveways, and limited on-street parking.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole	Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.12 m
		Light extension offset	0.5 m, $\alpha = 75^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base			
Pessl rain bucket:	$x = 0.41$ m, $z = 3.16$ m, $\alpha = 0^\circ$	Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	$x = 0.37$ m, $z = 3.04$ m, $\alpha = 35^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2025-12-03 12:45 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C6A	2025-12-03 12:30 to 2025-12-03 13:45 UTC Station installation

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs
From North
(2025-12-03)

From East
(2025-12-03)

From South
(2025-12-03)

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2025-12-03)

Bristol – Castle Park (BRCAPA)**Station location and siting**

Station ID	BRCAPA	Full name	Bristol – Castle Park
Latitude	51.455653°N	Longitude	2.5886009°W
Topographic elevation	18.6 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Castle Park, Bristol BS2 0HQ, UK	Administrative unit	Central
Local Climate Zone	D (Low plants)*	Urban Atlas Class	14100
Sky view factor	0.767	Dominant land use	Park
Orographic setting	Flat at valley bottom	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	50 m	Parking space:	150 m
		Tree:	35 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Popular and medium-sized inner-city greenspace. Open public area with grass, hedges and trees, pedestrian pathways. Park has microtopography and is located next to River Avon.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Blue surveillance camera pole		Material	Metal	
Height of structure	7 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.16 m	Light extension offset	rotating camera, ~ 0.1m offset
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base					
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.43 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 55^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 90^\circ$	

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-23 17:00 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C75	2024-05-23 17:00 UTC Station installation
			2025-05-28 07:30 UTC Station stopped transmitting
			2025-06-06 13:00 to 2025-06-06 13:00 UTC Service: Battery replacement
			2025-10-27 11:55 to 2025-10-27 12:10 UTC Service: Cleaning, blocked rain gauge

* Park area only

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-23)

From East
(2024-05-23)

From South
(2024-05-23)

From West
(2024-05-23)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-23)

Bristol – City Centre (BRCENT)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRCENT	Full name	Bristol – City Centre
Latitude	51.4563926°N	Longitude	2.5947221°W
Topographic elevation	9.4 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Drake House, Nelson St, Bristol BS1 2JT, UK	Administrative unit	Central
Local Climate Zone	2 (Compact midrise)	Urban Atlas Class	12100
Sky view factor	0.271	Dominant land use	Commercial
Orographic setting	Flat in valley bottom at base of slope in the NW	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	2 m	Parking space:	10 m
		Tree:	25 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Central business / commercial district with dense development and high-rise buildings. Station is located on curved canyon with tall 7+ story buildings on both sides.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Dark grey lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	11 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.11 m	Light extension offset 0.4 m, $\alpha = 150^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.41 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 15^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.37 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 50^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-21 12:00 UTC	2024-09-19 14:00 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C56	2024-05-21 12:00 UTC Station installation
2024-09-19 15:00 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C43	2024-09-07 23:00 UTC Station stopped transmitting (sensor damage)
			2024-09-19 10:10 to 2024-09-19 10:40 UTC Sensor swap

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
Not available

From East
(2024-05-21)

From South
(2024-05-21)

From West
(2024-05-21)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-21)

Bristol – Clifton Down (BRCLDO)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRCLDO	Full name	Bristol – Clifton Down
Latitude	51.472988°N	Longitude	2.621345°W
Topographic elevation	95.2 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Stoke Rd, Bristol BS9 1FG, UK	Administrative unit	Stoke Bishop
Local Climate Zone	D (Low plants)	Urban Atlas Class	14200
Sky view factor	0.653	Dominant land use	Recreational
Orographic setting	Flat on hilltop	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	1100 m	Parking space:	8 m
		Tree:	8 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Large hilltop open recreational grass area with sports fields. Station located on two-way road with trees.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Dark grey lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	9 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.11 m	Light extension offset 1.5 m, $\alpha = 35^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.41 m, z = 3.14 m, $\alpha = 145^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.37 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 180^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-16 18:20 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C62	2024-05-16 18:20 UTC Station installation
			2024-10-04 10:30 to 2024-10-04 10:60 UTC Service: Battery replacement
			2025-05-30 14:00 to 2025-05-30 14:10 UTC Service: Battery replacement
			2025-11-18 13:05 to 2025-11-18 13:15 UTC Service: Battery replacement
			2026-02-10 11:10 to 2026-02-10 11:20 UTC Service: Battery replacement, cleaning
			Comment: This site has poor reception with intermittent transmission loss

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-16)

From East
(2024-05-16)

From South
(2024-05-16)

From West
(2024-05-16)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-16)

Bristol – Clifton (BRCLIF)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRCLIF	Full name	Bristol – Clifton
Latitude	51.457536°N	Longitude	2.617004°W
Topographic elevation	71.9 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	35 Vyvyan Rd, Clifton, Bristol BS8 3AN, UK	Administrative unit	Clifton
Local Climate Zone	2 (Compact midrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.564	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Slight slope to E	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	6 m	Parking space:	2 m
		Tree:	2 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Historical mixed-use district next to Avon Gorge and suspension bridge. Station located on NE-SW oriented road with mostly 4-story attached row buildings and some vegetated front- and backyards.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Black lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	5 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset 1.5 m, $\alpha = 320^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.69 m, $\alpha = 220^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.57 m, $\alpha = 255^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-21 12:00 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C5F	2024-05-21 12:00 UTC Station installed
			2024-10-04 11:10 UTC Service: Battery replacement
			2024-11-27 15:15 UTC Service: Cleaning, funnel was slightly clogged, removed debris
			2025-11-18 13:30 to 2025-11-18 13:40 UTC Service: Battery replacement, Cleaning. Filter was pretty mucky, although water was still getting through.

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-21)

From East
(2024-05-21)

From South
Not available

From West
(2024-05-21)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-21)

Bristol – Cumberland Basin (BRCUBA)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRCUBA	Full name	Bristol – Cumberland Basin
Latitude	51.44937°N	Longitude	2.624132°W
Topographic elevation	8.2 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Administrative unit Hotwells and Harbourside		
Local Climate Zone	E (Bare rock or paved)*	Urban Atlas Class	12100
Sky view factor	0.829	Dominant land use	Industrial / Port / Transit
Orographic setting	Flat at entrance to gorge	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	10 m	Parking space:	-
		Tree:	50 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Transit and port area on entrance gorge. Station located on paved area between the river Avon and Cumberland Basin, next to lock.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Black lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	10 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset 0.5 m, $\alpha = 295^\circ$ 0.5 m, $\alpha = 115^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.41m, z = 3.36 m, $\alpha = 45^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.37 m, z = 3.24 m, $\alpha = 80^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-21 11:40 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13D47	2024-05-21 11:40 UTC Station installation
			2024-10-04 10:30 UTC Service: Battery replacement
			2024-11-21 15:20 to 2024-11-21 15:30 UTC Service: Battery replacement
			2026-02-10 12:15 to 2026-02-10 12:25 UTC Service: Battery replacement, cleaning

* Just immediate station surrounding, more complex mix on local scale

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-21)

From East
(2024-05-21)

From South
(2024-05-21)

From West
(2024-05-21)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-21)

Bristol – Eastgate (BREGAT)**Station location and siting**

Station ID	BREGAT	Full name	Bristol – Eastgate
Latitude	51.472572°N	Longitude	2.5688°W
Topographic elevation	16.4 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Eastgate Rd, Bristol BS5 6XX, UK	Administrative unit	Lockleaze
Local Climate Zone	8 (Large low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	12100
Sky view factor	0.812	Dominant land use	Industrial/Commercial
Orographic setting	Flat at base of hillslope in the NW	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	30 m	Parking space:	5 m
		Tree:	16 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Large light industrial / commercial area dominated by warehouse buildings and stores with large parking spaces and some vegetation.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Black lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	10 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.11 m	Light extension offset 0.4 m, $\alpha = 20^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.41 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 115^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.37 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 150^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-16 16:40 UTC	2025-01-31 14:40 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C70	2024-05-16 16:40 UTC Station installation
2025-01-31 15:00 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13D45	2024-08-19 04:45 UTC Station lost transmission
			2025-01-31 14:20 to 2025-01-31 14:40 UTC Sensor swap, battery replaced

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-16)

From East
(2024-05-16)

From South
(2024-05-16)

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-16)

Bristol – Emersons Green (BREMER)**Station location and siting**

Station ID	BREMER	Full name	Bristol – Emersons Green
Latitude	51.488455°N	Longitude	2.480811°W
Topographic elevation	67.0 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	119C Guest Ave, Emersons Green, Bristol BS16 7DA, UK	Administrative unit	South Gloucestershire, Emersons Green
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11220
Sky view factor	0.956	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	5 m	Parking space:	10 m
		Tree:	5 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Outer suburban residential area with post-war housing estates and semi-detached homes. Medium-sized gardens and green buffers. Station on a residential access road with 2-story houses, driveways, and intermittent street parking.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole	Material	Metal
Height of structure	7 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m
		Light extension offset	0.5 m, $\alpha = 248^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base			
Pessl rain bucket:	$x = 0.39$ m, $z = 3.16$ m, $\alpha = 0^\circ$	Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	$x = 0.35$ m, $z = 3.04$ m, $\alpha = 35^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	2025-12-03 13:40 UTC Station installation
2025-12-03 13:40 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C8D	

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs
From North
(2025-12-03)

From East
(2025-12-03)

From South
(2025-12-03)

From West
(2025-12-03)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2025-12-03)

Bristol – Fenswood Farm (BRFENS)**Station location and siting**

Station ID	BRFENS	Full name	Bristol – Fenswood Farm
Latitude	51.423811°N	Longitude	2.670870°W
Topographic elevation	49.1 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Wild Country Ln, Long Ashton, Bristol BS41 9AG, United Kingdom	Administrative unit	Long Ashton
Local Climate Zone	B (Scattered trees)	Urban Atlas Class	23000
Sky view factor	0.766	Dominant land use	Agricultural
Orographic setting	Flat in valley bottom	Artificial heat sources	-
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	20 m	Parking space:	- m
		Tree:	1 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Agricultural / rural setting next to a farm. Station on small hill with grass surface, some surrounding trees and bushes, open fields to the S, forested area / railway to N			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Silver pole	Material	Metal
Height of structure	3.20m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m
		Light extension offset	-
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base			
Pessl rain bucket:	$x = 0.15 \text{ m}, z = 3.16 \text{ m}, \alpha = 60^\circ$	Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	$x = 0.12 \text{ m}, z = 3.04 \text{ m}, \alpha = 180^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-20 12:00 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C46	2024-05-20 12:00 UTC Station installed
			2025-03-31 Service: Documentation, inspection, rain gauge fine
			2025-04-02 11:10 to 2025-04-02 11:20 UTC Service: Battery replacement

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2025-03-31)

From East
(2025-03-31)

From South
(2025-03-31)

From West
(2025-03-31)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2025-03-31)

Bristol – Filwood (BRFILW)**Station location and siting**

Station ID	BRFILW	Full name	Bristol – Filwood
Latitude	51.426307°N	Longitude	2.589355°W
Topographic elevation	63.3 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	12 Wicklow Rd, Bristol BS4 1JY, UK	Administrative unit	Filwood
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	12220
Sky view factor	0.802	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Hilltop	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	8 m	Parking space:	2 m
		Tree:	35 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Uniform inner suburban area. Station located on typical NE-SW-oriented street in with detached 2-3-story duplex houses and medium to large gardens.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset 1 m, $\alpha = 150^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.26 m, $\alpha = 80^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.14 m, $\alpha = 115^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-20 17:30 UTC	2025-05-02 13:41 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C76	2024-05-20 17:30 UTC Station installed
2025-05-02 14:05 UTC	2025-12-16 12:00 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13CA1	2025-05-02 14:00 to 2025-05-02 14:40 UTC Sensor swap due to damage / vandalism, battery replacement
2025-12-16 14:00 UTC	2026-03-24 12:00 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C66	2025-12-16 12:00 UTC Sensor swap due to damage / vandalism, battery replacement
2026-03-24 14:00 UTC	-	Pessl LoRAIN 03A0E51D	2026-03-24 13:30 to 2026-03-24 14:00 Sensor swap due to damage / vandalism, battery replacement, station relocated due to repeated vandalism

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-20)

From East
(2024-05-20)

From South
(2024-05-20)

From West
(2024-05-20)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-20)

Bristol – St George (BRGEOR)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRGEOR	Full name	Bristol – St George
Latitude	51.459533°N	Longitude	2.526464°W
Topographic elevation	82.0 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	21 Avening Rd, Bristol BS15 8AU, UK	Administrative unit	St George Central
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.747	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Slight slope to W	Artificial heat sources	
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	8 m	Parking space:	2 m
		Tree:	-
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Uniform residential area with primary duplex houses. Station located on E-W-oriented street with 2-3-story duplex houses and with large gardens.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Dark grey lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset 0.7 m, $\alpha = 175^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 255^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 290^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-21 18:30 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C8F	2024-05-21 18:30 UTC Station installation
			2024-09-14 10:15 UTC Station stopped transmitting data
			2025-03-30 15:40 to 2025-03-30 16:00 UTC Service: Battery replacement
			2025-10-27 15:03 to 2025-10-27 15:10 UTC Service: Cleaning, blocked rain gauge

Maps

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-21)

From East
(2024-05-21)

From South
(2024-05-21)

From West
(2024-05-21)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-21)

Bristol – Henleaze (BRHENL)**Station location and siting**

Station ID	BRHENL	Full name	Bristol – Henleaze
Latitude	51.487866°N	Longitude	2.605911°W
Topographic elevation	68.3 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	79 Park Grove, Westbury on Trym, Bristol BS9 4NY, UK	Administrative unit	Westbury on Trym and Henleaze
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	11220
Sky view factor	0.749	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Slight slope to NW	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	7 m	Parking space:	3 m
		Tree:	15 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Suburban residential area with primarily detached and some duplex houses and large gardens. Station located on typical N-S oriented road, 2-storey residential buildings with front gardens and boardwalk.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Dark grey lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset 0.8 m, $\alpha = 100^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 25^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 60^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-17 10:40 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C9A	2024-05-17 10:40 UTC Station installation
			2025-05-19 21:15 UTC Station stopped transmitting data
			2025-05-30 14:25 to 2025-05-30 14:30 UTC Service: Battery replacement
			2025-06-25 13:50 to 2025-06-25 14:00 UTC Service: Battery replacement

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-17)

From East
(2024-05-17)

From South
(2024-05-17)

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-17)

Bristol – Hillfields (BRHIFI)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRHIFI	Full name	Bristol – Hillfields
Latitude	51.4745°N	Longitude	2.51412°W
Topographic elevation	92.4 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	36 Hillfields Ave, Bristol BS16 4JR, UK	Administrative unit	Hillfields
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	12220
Sky view factor	0.726	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Slight slope to NW	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	8 m	Parking space:	3 m
		Tree:	20 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Uniform suburban residential area with primarily duplex houses and large gardens typical for Eastern side of Bristol. Station located on N-S-oriented street with 2-3-story buildings and front gardens.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Dark grey lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	11 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.11 m	Light extension offset 1.5 m, $\alpha = 270^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.41 m, z = 3.26 m, $\alpha = 145^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.37 m, z = 3.14 m, $\alpha = 180^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-21 18:00 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C6E	2024-05-21 18:00 UTC Station installation
			2025-10-27 14:40 to 2025-10-27 14:50 UTC Service: Battery replacement, cleaning, blocked rain gauge
			2025-10-29 18:30 UTC Station stopped transmitting data
			2025-12-03 14:05 to 2025-12-03 14:15 UTC Service: System restart, battery replacement

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-21)

From East
(2024-05-21)

From South
(2024-05-21)

From West
(2024-05-21)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-21)

Bristol – Horfield (BRHORF)**Station location and siting**

Station ID	BRHORF	Full name	Bristol – Horfield
Latitude	51.495495°N	Longitude	2.571811°W
Topographic elevation	76.9 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	1 Buxton Walk, Bristol BS7 0LG, UK	Administrative unit	Lockleaze
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	12220
Sky view factor	0.781	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	6 m	Parking space:	3 m
		Tree:	4 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Suburban residential area with duplex buildings and several construction styles. Station located on N-S-oriented road with cul-de-sac, 2 story houses with front gardens and drive ways, shrubs and hedges next to station.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Black lamp post		Material	Metal	
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset	0.6 m, $\alpha = 60^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base					
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.14 m, $\alpha = 130^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 185^\circ$	

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-17 13:00 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C5E	2024-05-17 13:00 UTC Station installation
			2025-05-30 14:45 to 2025-05-30 14:50 UTC Service: Battery replacement

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-17)

From East
(2024-05-17)

From South
(2024-05-17)

From West
(2024-05-17)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-17)

Bristol – Iron Acton (BRIRAC)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRIRAC	Full name	Bristol – Iron Acton
Latitude	51.550583 °N	Longitude	2.459181°W
Topographic elevation	66.0 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	B4059, Iron Acton, Bristol, UK	Administrative unit	South Gloucestershire, Frampton Cotterell
Local Climate Zone	B (Scattered trees)	Urban Atlas Class	21000
Sky view factor	0.918	Dominant land use	Transit / Agricultural
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	- m	Parking space:	- m
		Tree:	2 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Rural area next to multi-lane transit B4058 road. Area is sparsely built, with agricultural fields, retail areas, and the small village of Iron Acton to the South. Surroundings include large roads and commercial plots rather than continuous housing. Next to a hedge.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	10 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.18 m	Light extension offset 0.6 m, $\alpha = 45^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.44 m, z = 3.4 m, $\alpha = 115^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.4 m, z = 3.28 m, $\alpha = 150^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2025-11-26 15:10 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C67	2025-11-26 15:10 UTC Station installation

Maps

Photographs

<p>Street-level photographs From North (2025-11-26)</p>	
<p>From South (2025-11-26)</p>	

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2025-11-26)

Bristol – Knowle (BRKNOW)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRKNOW	Full name	Bristol – Knowle
Latitude	51.428954°N	Longitude	2.572286°W
Topographic elevation	55.2 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	39 Queenshill Rd, Bristol BS4 2XL, UK	Administrative unit	Knowle
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.748	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Hilltop, slope to S	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	5 m	Parking space:	1 m
		Tree:	10 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Residential inner suburban area with uniform duplex buildings typical for the S of Bristol. Station located on road with duplex 2-3-story residential buildings, medium trees and larger vegetated back gardens.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Black lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset 1 m, $\alpha = 350^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 135^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 170^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-20 16:40 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C48	2024-05-20 16:40 UTC Station installation
			2024-08-15 14:00 to 2024-08-15 14:10 UTC Service: Battery replacement
			2025-12-16 12:10 to 2025-12-16 12:25 UTC Service: Battery replacement, cleaning

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-20)

From East
(2024-05-20)

From South
(2024-05-20)

From West
(2024-05-20)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-20)

Bristol – Landsdowne Court (BRLACO)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRLACO	Full name	Bristol – Landsdowne Court
Latitude	51.460973°N	Longitude	2.569356°W
Topographic elevation	17.9 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	36 Pountney Dr, Easton, Bristol BS5 0XG, UK	Administrative unit	Lawrence Hill
Local Climate Zone	4 (Open high-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.686	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat in valley bottom	Artificial heat sources	None
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	25 m	Parking space:	5 m
		Tree:	12 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Inner-city urban renewal area with isolated high-rise and low-rise developments. Station located next two parking lot with residential high-rise buildings to the W. Area has a lot of ground vegetation and some mature trees.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Black lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	10 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.11 m	Light extension offset 1.2 m, $\alpha = 155^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.41 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 65^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.37 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 100^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-21 13:15 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C92	2024-05-21 13:15 UTC Station installation
			2024-12-19 Station stopped transmitting
			2025-03-30 15:30 to 2025-03-30 15:40 UTC Service: Battery replacement, cleaning
			2025-10-27 12:55 to 2025-10-27 13:07 UTC Service: Cleaning, blocked rain gauge, rain gauge filled with water.
			2026-02-10 12:55 to 2026-02-10 13:07 UTC Service: Cleaning, blocked rain gauge, filter completely clogged.

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-21)

From East
(2024-05-21)

From South
(2024-05-21)

From West
(2024-05-21)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-21)

Bristol – Leigh Woods (BRLEWO)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRLEWO	Full name	Bristol – Leigh Woods
Latitude	51.462523 °N	Longitude	2.639256 °W
Topographic elevation	101.7 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address		Administrative unit	North Somerset, Long Ashton
Local Climate Zone	A (Dense trees)	Urban Atlas Class	31000
Sky view factor	0.587	Dominant land use	Forest
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	-
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	- m	Parking space:	- m
		Tree:	2 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Dense woodland (Leigh Woods National Nature Reserve) with tall trees. Station is installed in a small clearing inside a densely forested area.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Tripod		Material	Metal	
Height of structure	3 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset	-
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base					
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.15 m, z = 2.9 m, $\alpha = 0^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.12 m, z = 2.78 m, $\alpha = 35^\circ$	

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2026-02-26 16:10 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13CA1	2026-02-26 16:10 UTC Station installation
			2026-05-12 10:30 to 2026-05-12 10:54 UTC Service: Battery replacement, cleaning

Maps

Photographs

<p>Street-level photographs From North Not available</p>	
<p>From South (2026-02-26)</p>	

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2026-02-26)

Bristol – Lower Easton (BRLOEA)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRLOEA	Full name	Bristol – Lower Easton
Latitude	51.466652°N	Longitude	2.562766°W
Topographic elevation	15.1 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	55 High St, Easton, Bristol BS5 6DW, UK	Administrative unit	Easton
Local Climate Zone	3 (Compact low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.610	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Slight slope to W	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	5 m	Parking space:	2 m
		Tree:	15 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Uniform inner-city suburban area with typical terraced houses. Station located in an E-W-oriented street canyon with 2-story row buildings and small front gardens.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Black lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	7 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset 1.5 m, $\alpha = 180^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.26 m, $\alpha = 110^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.14 m, $\alpha = 145^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-21 14:30 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C94	2024-05-21 14:30 UTC Station installation
			2025-10-27 13:15 to 2025-10-27 13:30 UTC Service: Cleaning, battery replacement

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
Not available

From East
(2024-05-21)

From South
(2024-05-21)

From West
(2024-05-21)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-21)

Bristol – Montpellier (BRMONT)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRMONT	Full name	Bristol – Montpellier
Latitude	51.470466°N	Longitude	2.594589°W
Topographic elevation	27.9 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	1A Cranbrook Rd, Redland, Bristol BS6 7BJ, United Kingdom	Administrative unit	Redland
Local Climate Zone	3 (Compact low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	12220
Sky view factor	0.731	Dominant land use	Residential/Commercial
Orographic setting	In tributary valley with slope to S	Artificial heat sources	cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	2 m	Parking space:	15 m
		Tree:	17 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Hillside residential / mixed area with dense development and residential / commercial use to the S and more open-set development to the N. Station located along NW-SE oriented road, 1-2-story, mostly duplex buildings (residential and shops) some with front yards and vegetated backyards.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Dark grey lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	10 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.13 m	Light extension offset 1.5 m, $\alpha = 45^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.42 m, z = 3.26 m, $\alpha = 205^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.38 m, z = 3.14 m, $\alpha = 240^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-17 18:10 UTC	2025-01-31 15:45 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C58	2024-05-17 18:10 UTC Station installation
2025-01-31 16:00 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C77	2025-01-31 15:00 to 2025-01-31 15:45 UTC Sensor swap, battery replacement
			2025-06-25 14:00 UTC Service: Battery replacement
			2026-11-18 12:40 to 2026-11-18 12:50 UTC Service: Filter was pretty clean, water was run through as a test.
			2026-01-20 12:10 to 2026-01-20 12:20 UTC Service: Battery replacement, Cleaning, System restart. Filter was pretty clean.
			2026-03-18 15:08 to 2026-03-18 15:11 UTC Service: Battery replacement, Cleaning

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-17)

From East
(2024-05-17)

From South
(2024-05-17)

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-17)

Bristol – Old Market (BROLDM)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BROLDM	Full name	Bristol – Old Market
Latitude	51.458091°N	Longitude	2.5802238°W
Topographic elevation	14.4 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Great Ann St Bristol BS2 0DX, UK	Administrative unit	Lawrence Hill
Local Climate Zone	4 (Open high-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.532	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat in valley bottom	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	17 m	Parking space:	1 m
		Tree:	15 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Inner-city residential area with large multi-unit buildings. Station next to parking lot with large 9-storey building in the SE.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey/blue lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	11 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.11m	Light extension offset 2 m, $\alpha = 125^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.41 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 15^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.37 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 50^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-21 12:30 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C71	2024-05-21 12:30 UTC Station installation
			2025-06-25 15:30 to 2025-06-25 15:40 UTC Service: Battery replacement

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-21)

From East
(2024-05-21)

From South
(2024-05-21)

From West
(2024-05-21)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-21)

Bristol – St Pauls (BRPAUL)**Station location and siting**

Station ID	BRPAUL	Full name	Bristol – St Pauls
Latitude	51.464048°N	Longitude	2.585626°W
Topographic elevation	16.9 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	112 City Rd, St Paul's, Bristol BS2 8UN, UK	Administrative unit	Ashley
Local Climate Zone	2 (Compact midrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.457	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat at base of slope in N	Artificial heat sources	cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	2 m	Parking space:	2 m
		Tree:	15 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Historical inner-city area with uniform row-houses. Station located along NE-SW oriented Street with 3-story row buildings and sparsely vegetated front and back gardens.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Black lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	15 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.12 m	Light extension offset 2 m, $\alpha = 320^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.41 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 290^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.37 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 325^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-22 15:10 UTC	2025-01-31 13:50 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C8D	2024-05-22 15:10 UTC Station installation
2025-01-31 15:00 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C72	2025-01-31 13:50 to 2025-01-31 15:00 UTC Sensor swap, battery replacement

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-22)

From East
(2024-05-22)

From South
Not available

From West
(2024-05-22)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-22)

Bristol – St Philips Marsh (BRPHIL)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRPHIL	Full name	Bristol – St Philips Marsh
Latitude	51.448117°N	Longitude	2.570008°W
Topographic elevation	8.7 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Albert Cres, Bristol BS2 0UW, UK	Administrative unit	Lawrence Hill
Local Climate Zone	8 (Large low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	12100
Sky view factor	0.829	Dominant land use	Industrial
Orographic setting	Flat in valley bottom	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	2 m	Parking space:	1 m
		Tree:	15 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Largest inner-city warehouse / industrial district in Bristol. Station located in centre of industrial/warehouse area on N-S-oriented street in with 1-2 story industrial / warehouses and some vegetation next to station.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Dark lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	12 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.09 m	Light extension offset 1.5 m, $\alpha = 290^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 30^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.31 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 65^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-23 10:50 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C6B	2024-05-23 10:50 UTC Station installation
			2024-07-25 04:15 Station stopped transmission
			2024-08-15 13:50 to 2024-08-15 14:20 UTC Service: Battery replacement
			2025-03-31 15:15 to 2025-03-31 15:25 UTC Service: cleaning
			2025-10-27 12:29 to 2025-10-27 12:42 UTC Service: Cleaning, blocked rain gauge, rain gauge full of water
			2025-12-16 10:40 to 2025-12-16 10:55 UTC Service: Battery replacement, cleaning, T/RH screen dirty

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2025-03-31)

From East
(2025-03-31)

From South
(2024-05-23)

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-23)

Bristol – Queen Square (BRQUSQ)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRQUSQ	Full name	Bristol – Queen Square
Latitude	51.4505041°N	Longitude	2.5949375°W
Topographic elevation	10.4 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Queen Square, Bristol BS1 4LH, UK	Administrative unit	Central
Local Climate Zone	B (Scattered trees)*, 2 (Compact midrise)**	Urban Atlas Class	14100
Sky view factor	0.542	Dominant land use	Park
Orographic setting	Flat, in valley bottom	Artificial heat sources	-
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	- m	Parking space:	- m
		Tree:	25 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Small historical public park with monument and star-shaped path network, tall trees, gravel and grass surfaces surrounded by historical 4-storey buildings. Station located in centre of park.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Black lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	4 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.12 m	Light extension offset 0.15 m, all directions
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = m, z = m, $\alpha = \circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = m, z = m, $\alpha = \circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-23 16:00 UTC	2025-02-12 15:00 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C49	2024-05-23 16:00 UTC Station installation
2025-02-12 15:10 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C6C	2025-02-12 14:45 to 2025-02-12 15:10 UTC Sensor swap, Battery replacement
			2025-10-27 11:05 to 2025-10-27 11:25 UTC Service: Battery replacement, cleaning, blocked rain gauge
			2025-10-28 10:05 to 2025-10-28 10:15 UTC Service: Blocked rain gauge
			General comment: Due to form of street light, the rain gauge measurement is impacted.

* Park area only, **Sourrounding

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2025-02-12)

From East
(2025-02-12)

From South
(2025-02-12)

From West
(2025-02-12)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-23)

Bristol – Redcliffe (BRREDC)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRREDC	Full name	Bristol – Redcliffe
Latitude	51.451236°N	Longitude	2.587809°W
Topographic elevation	8.9 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	19 Mitchell Ct, Redcliffe, Bristol, UK	Administrative unit	Central
Local Climate Zone	2 (Compact midrise)	Urban Atlas Class	12100
Sky view factor	0.231	Dominant land use	Commercial
Orographic setting	Flat, in valley bottom	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	2 m	Parking space:	1 m
		Tree:	-
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Inner-city dense developed commercial / institutional area. Station located along N-S-oriented lane (street canyon) with 6-storey buildings in east and west direction.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Black lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	8 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset 0.7 m, $\alpha = 85^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.14 m, $\alpha = 175^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.06 m, $\alpha = 210^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-23 15:20 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C68	2024-05-23 15:20 UTC Station installation
			2024-08-15 15:00 to 2024-08-15 15:10 UTC Service: Battery replacement
			2025-04-01 16:15 to 2025-04-01 17:30 UTC Service: Battery replacement
			2025-10-27 11:35 to 2025-10-27 11:47 UTC Service: Cleaning, blocked rain gauge
			2025-12-03 10:45 to 2025-12-03 10:55 UTC Service: System restart, battery replacement

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-23)

From East
(2024-05-23)

From South
Not available

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-23)

Bristol – Redland (BRREDL)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRREDL	Full name	Bristol – Redland
Latitude	51.466348°N	Longitude	2.603259°W
Topographic elevation	49.9 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	2 Rokeby Ave, Redland, Bristol BS6 6EL, UK	Administrative unit	Cotham
Local Climate Zone	3 (Compact low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.665	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	2 m	Parking space:	2 m
		Tree:	>20 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
NW-SE oriented street with 2-story residential duplex buildings (dense) with vegetated front and back gardens (shrubs)			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Dark grey lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset 1 m, $\alpha = 55^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 165^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 190^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-22 14:20 UTC	2025-05-02 14:43 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C5A	2024-05-22 14:20 UTC Station installation
2025-05-02 15:00 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C47	2024-11-27 14:45 to 2024-11-27 15:00 GMT Service: Checked rain gauge, manually tipped bucket
			2025-05-02 15:00 to 2025-05-02 15:30 UTC Sensor swap, battery replaced
			2025-11-18 12:10 to 2025-11-18 12:30 UTC Rain gauge blocked, Service: cleaning, battery replacement, rain gauge full of water.

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-22)

From East
(2024-05-22)

From South
(2024-05-22)

From West
(2024-05-22)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-22)

Bristol – Royal Fort Gardens (BRROFO)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRROFO	Full name	Bristol – Royal Fort Gardens
Latitude	51.4579609°N	Longitude	2.6018101°W
Topographic elevation	78.2 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Bristol BS8 1UH, United Kingdom	Administrative unit	Central
Local Climate Zone	5 (Open mid-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	12100
Sky view factor	0.552	Dominant land use	Park
Orographic setting	Flat on top of hill	Artificial heat sources	-
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	7 m	Parking space:	- m
		Tree:	15 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Centre of University of Bristol campus. Station located on plaza between large buildings to N and S, embedded in the Royal Fort Gardens (highly vegetated).			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Black lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	4.5 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset
				0.2 m, all sides
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 210^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 245^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2023-12-28 12:00 UTC	2024-05-22 11:59 UTC	Pessl LoRAIN 03A0E517	2023-12-28 12:00 UTC Station installed
2024-05-22 12:00 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C6F	2024-02-23 15:00 UTC Battery replacement
			2024-05-22 12:00 UTC Sensor swapped
			2024-11-22 13:30 to 2024-11-22 13:45 UTC Service: Battery replacement
			2025-12-16 10:15 to 2025-12-16 10:26 UTC Service: Battery replacement, filter checked

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2025-04-03)

From East
(2025-04-03)

From South
(2025-04-03)

From West
(2025-04-03)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2025-04-03)

Bristol – Severnside (BRSEVS)**Station location and siting**

Station ID	BRSEVS	Full name	Bristol – Severnside
Latitude	51.563601°N	Longitude	2.666079 °W
Topographic elevation	5.0 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	75A Beach Rd Severn Beach, Bristol BS35 4PE	Administrative unit	South Gloucestershire, Pilning & Severn Beach
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.933	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	flat	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	5 m	Parking space:	2 m
		Tree:	5 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Seaside / seawall setting in village (Severn Beach). Two-story houses on the east side of the street.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.1 m	Light extension offset 0.4 m, $\alpha = 285^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.4 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 0^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.36 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 35^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2025-11-24 15:40 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C42	

Maps

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2025-11-24)

From East
(2025-11-24)

From South
(2025-11-24)

From West
(2025-11-24)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2025-11-24)

Bristol – Stoke Gifford (BRSGIF)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRSGIF	Full name	Bristol – Stoke Gifford
Latitude	51.520110°N	Longitude	2.543479°W
Topographic elevation	55.0 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	14 Tybalt Way, Stoke Gifford, Bristol BS34 8XJ, UK	Administrative unit	South Gloucestershire, Stoke Gifford
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.920	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	4 m	Parking space:	1 m
		Tree:	7 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Outer suburban residential area. Consistent two-story brick constructions with small to medium gardens.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey light pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.1m	Light extension offset 0.4m, $\alpha = 205^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.4 m, z = 3.16m, $\alpha = 0^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.36 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 35^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2025-11-26 16:05 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C78	2025-11-26 16:05 UTC Station installation

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2025-11-26)

From East
(2025-11-26)

From South
(2025-11-26)

From West
(2025-11-26)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2025-11-26)

Bristol – St Georges Park (BRSGPA)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRSGPA	Full name	Bristol – St Georges Park
Latitude	51.461674°N After 2026-03-24: 51.461380°N	Longitude	2.547693°W After 2026-03-24: 2.547901°W
Topographic elevation	38.2 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Church Rd, Whitehall, Bristol BS5 7AA, United Kingdom	Administrative unit	St Georges West
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open lowrise)	Urban Atlas Class	14100
Sky view factor	0.536 After 2026-03-24: 0.747	Dominant land use	Park
Orographic setting	flat	Artificial heat sources	-
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	- m	Parking space:	- m
		Tree:	5 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Park with grass surfaces and paved pathways, in north-east direction water body with 120 x 40m dimensions.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Silver pole		Material	Metal
Height of structure	5.5 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.08 m	Light extension offset 0.6 m, $\alpha = 0^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 5^\circ$ After 2026-03-24: x = 0.39 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 45^\circ$	Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 40^\circ$ After 2026-03-24: x = 0.35 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 80^\circ$	

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-22 16:00 UTC	2026-03-24 14:30 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C5B	2024-05-22 16:00 UTC Station installation
2026-03-24 14:50 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13D4A	2025-04-02 16:00 to 2025-04-02 16:20 UTC Service: quality assessment: Blocked rain gauge, Cleaning
			2025-10-27 13:40 to 2025-10-27 13:51 UTC Service: Cleaning, Blocked rain gauge, Battery replacement
			2025-12-16 11:05 to 2025-12-16 11:10 UTC Service: Cleaning, Blocked rain gauge
			2026-03-24 14:50 UTC Station relocation from 51.461674°N, 2.547693°W to 51.461380°N, 2.547901°W.

Maps

Photographs (before 2026-03-24)

Street-level photographs	
<p>From North (2024-05-22)</p>	
<p>From South (2024-05-22)</p>	

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-22)

Photographs (after 2026-03-24)

Street-level photographs

From North
(2026-03-24)

From East
(2026-03-24)

From South
(2026-03-24)

From West
(2026-03-24)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2026-03-24)

Bristol – Shirehampton (BRSHIR)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRSHIR	Full name	Bristol – Shirehampton
Latitude	51.486257°N	Longitude	2.675442°W
Topographic elevation	29.3 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	62 St Bernard's Rd, Shirehampton, Bristol BS11 9UL, UK	Administrative unit	Avonmouth and Larence Weston
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	11220
Sky view factor	0.792	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Slight slope to S	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	10 m	Parking space:	3 m
		Tree:	12 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Suburban area on Northern side of Avon Gorge characterized by 2-story residential multi-unit buildings with front and large back gardens. Station located on typical road orientated NE-SW.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.08 m	Light extension offset 0.4 m, $\alpha = 135^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 50^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 85^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-16 12:15 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C3F	2024-05-16 12:15 UTC Station installation
			2024-10-04 10:50 Service: Battery replacement
			2026-02-10 11:30 to 2026-02-10 11:50 UTC Service: Battery replacement, cleaning, filter already pretty clean.

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
Not available

From East
(2024-05-16)

From South
(2024-05-16)

From West
(2024-05-16)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-16)

Bristol – Southville (BRSOVI)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRSOVI	Full name	Bristol – Southville
Latitude	51.443484°N	Longitude	2.608023°W
Topographic elevation	13.6 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	54 Hamilton Rd, Southville, Bristol BS3 1PB, UK	Administrative unit	Southville
Local Climate Zone	3 (Compact low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.625	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Slope to NW	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	2 m	Parking space:	1 m
		Tree:	>20 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Dense and uniform inner-city residential area characterized by terraced houses. Station located on sloped NW-SE-oriented street with 2-story row buildings including small vegetated front and back yards.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Lamp post	Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m
		Light extension offset	0.8 m, $\alpha = 75^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base			
Pessl rain bucket:	$x = 0.39$ m, $z = 3.16$ m, $\alpha = 150^\circ$	Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	$x = 0.35$ m, $z = 3.04$ m, $\alpha = 185^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-23 12:45 UTC	2025-02-18 15:00 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C66	2024-05-23 12:45 UTC Station installation
2025-02-18 16:00 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C45	2024-08-14 13:40 to 2024-08-14 13:45 UTC Service: Battery replacement
			2025-02-18 15:00 to 2025-02-18 16:00 UTC Sensor swap, battery replacement
			2026-03-18 10:30 to 2026-03-18 10:38 UTC Service: Battery replacement, cleaning
			2026-04-23 11:40 to 2026-04-23 11:50 UTC Service: Battery replacement

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
not available

From East
(2025-04-03)

From South
(2025-04-03)

From West
Not available

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-23)

Bristol – Stanton Drew (BRSTAN)**Station location and siting**

Station ID	BRSTAN	Full name	Bristol – Stanton Drew
Latitude	51.365245 °N	Longitude	2.580357°W
Topographic elevation	48.1 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	Administrative unit Somerset, Stanton Drew		
Local Climate Zone	D (Low plants)	Urban Atlas Class	21000
Sky view factor	0.990	Dominant land use	Agricultural
Orographic setting	Flat, gentle northern slope	Artificial heat sources	-
Proximity to nearest...			
Building: - m Parking space: 30 m Tree: 15 m			
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Rural site on a meadow (25 x 100 m) with grass surrounded by small fence at the edge of a village (Stanton Drew).			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Tripod		Material	Metal
Height of structure	3 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset -
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:		x = 0.15 m, z = 2.9 m, $\alpha = 0^\circ$	Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.12 m, z = 2.78 m, $\alpha = 35^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	2026-04-23 13:45 UTC Station installed
2026-04-23 13:45 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C5B	

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2026-04-23)

From East
(2026-04-23)

From South
(2026-04-23)

From West
(2026-04-23)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2026-04-23)

Bristol – Stoke Bishop (BRSTBI)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRSTBI	Full name	Bristol – Stoke Bishop
Latitude	51.479912°N	Longitude	2.631256°W
Topographic elevation	37.4 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	5 Howecroft Gardens, Bristol BS9 1HN, UK	Administrative unit	Stoke Bishop
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	11220
Sky view factor	0.621	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Slight slope to NNW	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	m	Parking space:	m
		Tree:	m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Highly vegetated residential area with tall trees and large detached or duplex buildings. Station located on cul-de-sac with 2-storey duplex residential buildings with large front and back gardens, circular grass park with large tree in the centre, approx. 8 m from station.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Black lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset 0.4 m, $\alpha = 135^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 25^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 60^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-16 15:35 UTC	2025-02-03 16:30 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C99	2024-05-16 15:35 UTC Station installation
2025-02-03 17:00 UTC	2026-02-03 13:00 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C65	2025-02-02 Inspected station and identified it has been damaged, with base-plate case falling out. Having examined the instrument, water entered the battery compartment and caused the damage
2026-02-03 13:55 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C56	2025-02-03 16:30 to 2025-02-03 17:00 UTC Sensor swap, battery replacement
			2025-12-16 13:30 to 2025-12-16 14:00 UTC Service, Site has not been reporting data since the 2025-11-30. Sensor looks fine from a visual inspection. Quality assessment, system restart, no success
			2026-02-03 13:30 to 2026-02-03 13:55 UTC Sensor swap, battery replacement

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-16)

From East
(2024-05-16)

From South
(2024-05-16)

From West
(2024-05-16)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-16)

Bristol – Stockwood (BRSTOC)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRSTOC	Full name	Bristol – Stockwood
Latitude	51.415192°N	Longitude	2.544777°W
Topographic elevation	88.2 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	121 Stockwood Rd, Stockwood, Bristol BS14 8JH, UK	Administrative unit	Stockwood
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.799	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Slight slope to NW	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	15 m	Parking space:	20 m
		Tree:	10 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Low-density suburban area with detached 2-story houses. Station located on strip of grass next to a road.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Dark grey lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	10 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.13 m	Light extension offset 0.5 m, $\alpha = 330^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.42 m, z = 3.26 m, $\alpha = 135^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.38 m, z = 3.14 m, $\alpha = 170^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-20 15:25 UTC	2025-03-27 15:55 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C5C	2024-05-20 15:25 UTC Station installation
2025-03-27 16:05 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C64	2024-09-09 06:00 UTC Battery depleted, station stopped working
			2025-03-27 15:55 UTC Sensor swapped, battery replaced

Maps

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-20)

From East
(2024-05-20)

From South
(2024-05-20)

From West
(2024-05-20)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-20)

Bristol – Tyndalls Park (BRTYND)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRTYND	Full name	Bristol – Tyndalls Park
Latitude	51.4601498°N	Longitude	2.6020401°W
Topographic elevation	73.5 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	3 Osborne Villas, Bristol BS2 8BP, UK	Administrative unit	Central
Local Climate Zone	3 (Compact low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.588	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Flat, plateau	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	5 m	Parking space:	1 m
		Tree:	17 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Dense inner-city residential / institutional area next to University campus. Station on E-W-oriented road close to curve with 2-storey residential row (terraced) buildings, narrow front gardens.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Black lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset 0.5 m, $\alpha = 155^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 45^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 80^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-17 19:10 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C73	2024-05-17 19:10 UTC Station installation
			2024-09-16 13:25 to 2024-09-16 13:30 UTC Service: Battery replacement
			2025-11-18 13:50 to 2025-11-18 14:00 UTC Service: Battery replacement, cleaning. Filter in good shape. Tested by running water through.

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
Not available

From East
(2024-05-17)

From South
(2024-05-17)

From West
(2024-05-17)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-17)

Bristol – Tyntesfield (BRTYNT)**Station location and siting**

Station ID	BRTYNT	Full name	Bristol – Tyntesfield
Latitude	51.435901 °N	Longitude	2.710655 °W
Topographic elevation	53.1 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address		Administrative unit	North Somerset, Long Ashton
Local Climate Zone	B (Scattered trees)	Urban Atlas Class	23000
Sky view factor	0.990	Dominant land use	Agricultural
Orographic setting	Gentle south slope	Artificial heat sources	-
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	- m	Parking space:	- m
		Tree:	15 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Orchard in low-intensity agricultural / conservation land on an estate (Tyntesfield National Trust Site) characterized by tall grasses and seasonal herbaceous vegetation.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Tripod		Material	Metal	
Height of structure	3 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset	-
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base					
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.15 m, z = 2.9 m, $\alpha = 0^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.12 m, z = 2.78 m, $\alpha = 35^\circ$	

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	2026-02-26 10:15 UTC Station installation
2026-02-26 12:15 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C76	

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs
From North
(2026-02-26)

From East
(2026-02-26)

From South
(2026-02-26)

From West
(2026-02-26)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2026-02-26)

Bristol – Windmill Hill (BRWIMI)**Station location and siting**

Station ID	BRWIMI	Full name	Bristol – Windmill Hill
Latitude	51.4432723°N	Longitude	2.5804656°W
Topographic elevation	38.1 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	70 William St, Totterdown, Bristol BS3 4TX, UK	Administrative unit	Windmill Hill
Local Climate Zone	3 (Compact low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	11210
Sky view factor	0.583	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Slope to S	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	2 m	Parking space:	1 m
		Tree:	>20 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Dense inner-city residential area characterized by uniform row buildings. Station located along NE-SW-oriented street with 2-story buildings, some with small front gardens.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Black lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset 0.3 m, $\alpha = 320^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 60^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 95^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-23 12:00 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C8E	2024-05-23 12:00 UTC Station installed
			2024-06-10 13:00 UTC Service: Battery replaced

Maps

Position within urban network

Position on local-scale (500 m radius)

Aerial photograph of micro-scale surrounding

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2025-04-03)

From East
(2025-04-03)

From South
(not available)

From West
(2025-04-03)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-23)

Bristol – Withywood (BRWITH)

Station location and siting

Station ID	BRWITH	Full name	Bristol – Withywood
Latitude	51.413398°N	Longitude	2.617617°W
Topographic elevation	48.6 m	Elevation above ground	0 m
Address	52 Derham Rd, Bishopsworth, Bristol BS13 7SB, UK	Administrative unit	Hardcliffe and Withywood
Local Climate Zone	6 (Open low-rise)	Urban Atlas Class	12220
Sky view factor	0.799	Dominant land use	Residential
Orographic setting	Slight slope to NE	Artificial heat sources	Cars
Proximity to nearest...			
Building:	15 m	Parking space:	10 m
		Tree:	8 m
Surrounding land cover and surface description			
Suburban residential area with duplexes (2-story buildings) and large back and front gardens. Station located on cul-de-sac.			

Mounting structure characteristics

Type	Grey lamp post		Material	Metal
Height of structure	6 m	Diameter at mounting height	0.07 m	Light extension offset 0.7 m, $\alpha = 110^\circ$
Location of sensors relative to center of mounting structure base				
Pessl rain bucket:	x = 0.39 m, z = 3.16 m, $\alpha = 170^\circ$		Pessl Ta/RH sensor:	x = 0.35 m, z = 3.04 m, $\alpha = 205^\circ$

History and remarks (up to 2026-05-31)

Sensor history			Local maintenance / service events
Start date	End date	Sensor	
2024-05-20 14:00 UTC	2025-03-27 15:20 UTC	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C47	2024-05-20 14:00 UTC Station installation
2025-03-27 15:30 UTC	-	Pessl nMetos180 04D13C70	2024-09-06 05:00 UTC Station stopped working due to battery depletion
			2025-03-27 15:15 to 2025-03-27 15:30 UTC Sensor swap, battery replacement
			2026-03-18 12:05 to 2026-03-18 12:30 UTC Service: battery replacement, cleaning. Even after the cleaning the filter the tipping bucket still didn't operate properly. Turns out it was completely stuffed full of spiders web. After cleaning it started working again.

Maps

Photographs

Street-level photographs

From North
(2024-05-20)

From East
(2024-05-20)

From South
(2024-05-20)

From West
(2024-05-20)

Sky view photograph
on top of rain gauge
(2024-05-20)

